

Sustaining Traditions: Assam's Agricultural Heritage and Indigenous Paddy Varieties

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Abstract

Agriculture in Assam, northeastern India, is anchored in a centuries-old rice-based farming system sustained by Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) and extraordinary paddy diversity, yet this heritage faces accelerating erosion from modern agricultural interventions. This study aims to identify, document, and analyse the ITK practices and traditional paddy varieties historically cultivated across Assam's diverse agro-climatic zones, with particular focus on traditional tools, seasonal cropping systems, and the consequences of technological displacement. The study adopts a descriptive and analytical research design relying on secondary sources including government statistical handbooks (2005-2025), peer-reviewed literature in agronomy and ethnobotany, and institutional germplasm records from KVK and NBPGR. Thematic analysis was organised along the paddy production cycle and seasonal ecotype classification. Findings reveal 36 distinct ITK practices spanning eight agronomic categories from seed-bed preparation and water management to plant protection and post-harvest storage each grounded in functional ecological rationale. Assam contributes approximately 6,630 paddy accessions to the national gene bank and nearly 10% of India's total from a single state encompassing four principal ecotypes: Ahu, Sali, Bao, and Boro. Statistical data further show a 34% expansion in HYV cultivation area between 2005 and 2020 alongside a 53% rise in chemical fertiliser use directly eroding traditional varieties and organic soil management practices. The study concludes that Assam's traditional paddy systems constitute a scientifically coherent and ecologically resilient heritage of both regional and global significance, warranting urgent policy support, community seed banking, and integration of ITK into mainstream agricultural extension frameworks.

Keywords: *Indigenous Technical Knowledge, Traditional Paddy Varieties, Assam, Agroecology, HYV Adoption.*

Introduction

Agriculture remains a fundamental pillar of the Indian economy, employing nearly half of the country's workforce and forming a significant part of household expenditure [1]. Within this broader context, the North-Eastern Region (NER) of India stands out to its unique socio-cultural diversity and strong dependence on agriculture. In this region more than 70% of the population relies on agriculture for their livelihood, highlighting its central role in sustaining rural livelihood. Constituting approximately 7.98% of India's total geographical area while holding about 3.77% of its population, the NER is characterized by a food grain-oriented cropping pattern in which paddy holds the dominant share [2].

Among the northeastern states, Assam holds a prominent position due to its favourable agro-climatic conditions and rich natural resource base. The state is predominantly agrarian in nature, with agriculture deeply embedded in its socio-economic and cultural condition. Unlike many parts of India that are shifting towards industrial and service sectors, Assam yet continues to heavily depend on agriculture for livelihood and economic stability [3]. Paddy cultivation in particular dominates the agricultural landscape, making the state widely recognized for its paddy-based farming system [4].

Spanning 78,438 sq. km across six agro-climatic zones shaped by the Brahmaputra and Barak river systems, the state supports approximately 2.6 million farming families whose livelihoods are intimately tied to its land and water cycles [5]. At the heart of this agrarian landscape lies the rich rice-based farming system (RBFS), which is not merely a method of crop production but a deeply rooted cultural institution shaped by generations of knowledge, traditions, and community practices [6].

Over centuries farmers across Assam's diverse ecological zones have cultivated an extraordinary range of rice ecotypes such as aromatic Joha, semi-waxy Chokuwa, waxy Bora, and deep-water Bao and each of them are precisely adopted to its local environmental niches and community food traditions [4]. Maintaining this diversity has required a rich body of indigenous technical knowledge (ITK). Because of that farmers in Assam have developed and refined a wide range of cultivation techniques suited to their local environments. This accumulated knowledge widely known as Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) represents a valuable repository of traditional wisdom that shaped through continuous interaction with nature covering every stage of the farming cycle from seed selection to grain storage [7]. ITK in Assam is not merely practical knowledge but it is an ecological intelligence shaped by intimate, long-term observation of soil, water, climate, and biodiversity [8].

The contemporary relevance of traditional farming systems is increasingly recognised all over the world. As global agriculture confronts climate change, biodiversity erosion, and food insecurity, practices embedded in Assam's ITK like ecological pest regulation, organic soil management, water-

harvesting land shaping are very closely aligned with the principles of agroecology and climate-smart agriculture at present scenario [9], [10]. Yet precisely as ITK's value is being redefined globally, it is being eroded locally. After the introduction of the Green Revolution in the 1960s, the displacement of traditional methods also began, and since the late 1980s the adoption of High Yielding Variety (HYV) seeds, chemical fertilisers, and mechanised tillage has accelerated sharply in Assam which progressively marginalising indigenous cultivars and the knowledge systems that sustain them [11], [12].

Therefore, efforts to preserve and promote this knowledge should prioritize indigenous rights, self-determination, and equitable partnerships to ensure its respectful and ethical use. By doing so, we can ensure that Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) continues to contribute to sustainable development and the well-being of local communities. The identification and documentation of these scientifically sound indigenous practices and paddy varieties are essential not only for the successful implementation of technology-blending programs but also for developing cost-effective, appropriate technologies that can benefit farmers [8].

In recent years, scientists also have recognized that these indigenous peoples have long managed their ecosystems sustainably often without causing significant harm to the environment. This traditional knowledge offers a valuable basis for creating alternative resource management methods. By understanding and documenting both the scientific principles behind these practices and the ways in which they are communicated, we can help preserve these practices for future generations [9], [10].

The main purpose of this paper is to identify and document Indigenous Technical Knowledge and traditional paddy varieties used and cultivated by farmers in Assam from ancient times to the present. The study specifically focuses on the traditional agricultural tools and technologies employed by local communities [13], [14]. As modern tools and technologies increasingly replace these traditional methods, this paper aims to preserve and record this valuable knowledge before it is lost. By collecting reliable information on these practices and addressing the challenges faced by the community, the study seeks to ensure the preservation and appreciation of Assam's rich agricultural heritage.

Materials and Method

Study Area

Assam is situated in the north-eastern part of India, 20° N and 28° N latitude and 90° E and 96° E longitude, and covering a geographical area over 78,438 sq. km [15]. It is bordered by Bhutan and Arunachal Pradesh to the north, Nagaland and Manipur to the east, Meghalaya, Tripura, and Mizoram to the south, and West Bengal and Bangladesh to the west [16]. The state is physically defined by two major river systems the Brahmaputra in the north and the Barak in the south which together create the broad, alluvial floodplains that constitute the primary rice-growing landscape of the region [17].

Assam is one of India's agriculturally significant states due to its favourable natural and agro-climatic conditions. Based on variations in rainfall, soil, and physiography, Assam is divided into six agro-climatic zones: Upper Brahmaputra Valley, Central Brahmaputra Valley, Lower Brahmaputra Valley, North Bank Plain, Barak Valley, and Hill Zone [18]. These zones comprise diverse agricultural landscapes such as floodplains, wetlands, uplands, and hill slopes. The soils vary from fertile alluvial deposits in riverine tracts, highly suitable for rice cultivation, to red and lateritic soils in foothill areas. Agriculture supports nearly 2.6 million farming families, and rice remains the dominant crop in the cultivated area. Assam is also home to several ethnic communities, including Bodo, Mishing, Karbi, Dimasa, and Tiwa, whose traditional farming knowledge has contributed significantly to the development and conservation of indigenous paddy diversity [6]. Owing to its ecological diversity and rich socio-cultural heritage, Assam provides an important setting for the study of Indigenous Technical Knowledge and traditional paddy-based farming systems.

Figure-1: Agro-climatic map of Assam

Source: Source: Generated from Indian shape file (Admin) and Google Earth using ArcGIS methodology

This study employs descriptive and analytical methodologies appropriate to a documentation and assessment-based research design. As the principal aim here is to synthesise and interpret existing knowledge rather than generate new primary data because of what the research primarily relies on secondary sources, which provide the necessary breadth, historical depth, and quantitative range that needed to address the study's three primary enquiries.

There are four categories of secondary sources were consulted for this study i.e. (i) government publications- principally the Statistical Handbook of Assam (2005–2025) [19] and reports of the

Directorate of Agriculture, Assam for longitudinal data on HYV adoption, irrigated area, fertiliser consumption, and mechanisation (ii) peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings on agronomy, ethnobotany, and agro-biodiversity relating to Assam and Northeast India (iii) published books and edited volumes for historical and ethnographic context; and (iv) institutional repositories of the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (NBPGR), the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR), Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) data reports for germplasm records. Sources were selected on the basis of credibility, direct relevance to Assam's agricultural context and temporal coverage. Peer-reviewed and government-verified sources were consistently prioritised here. All local terminology is retained with standardised English equivalents in parentheses.

The analysis is organised thematically. The discussion of ITK practices (Section 4.2) follows the sequence of the paddy production cycle, framing traditional knowledge as a coherent, stage-by-stage management system. The germplasm discussion (Section 4.4) is organised by seasonal ecotype reflecting the ecological logic through which varieties were developed and maintained. The technology transition analysis (Section 4.5) draws on quantitative time-series data to assess the pace and direction of change, while Sections 4.6 offer integrative interpretations situating the empirical findings within the broader argument for sustaining traditional systems.

Results and Discussion

Agro-Ecological Foundations of Assam's Traditional paddy Culture

Agriculture in Assam is primarily governed by a complex interplay of ecological, climatic, and socio-economic factors. Situating in the monsoon belt of north-east India, the state's cropping calendar is mainly linked to its seasonal rhythm of rainfall, river flooding, and soil moisture. paddy occupies the central position in this agricultural system, covering the majority of the net sown area and sustaining the livelihoods of a large proportion of the rural population [11], [20]. The state generally follows two principal types of cropping seasons i.e. 1. Kharif season (summer/monsoon) and 2. Rabi season(winter). paddy dominates most of the agricultural landscape by occupying nearly 70-75% of the net sown area, and remains the most important crop in terms of area, production, and cultural significance [11], [20].

Traditional paddy cultivation in Assam developed through adaptation to its varied floodplain environmental conditions. Based on topography and seasonal water condition in Assam farmers here from ancient periods start cultivating primarily four types of major paddy groups namely – Ahu Dhan (autumn paddy), Sali & Bao Dhan (winter paddy), Boro Dhan (summer paddy). Out of these, Ahu Dhan is cultivated on intermediate lowlands (Madhyam Mati) where floodwaters reach approximately 0.35m. Sali Dhan occupies higher alluvial fields (Da Mati) with inundation up to 0.53m. Bao Dhan is uniquely adapted to the lowest lying flood prone areas tolerating floodwater depths of up to almost 0.88 m conditions that would destroy any other conventional crop. Then on

the other hand, Boro Dhan is a dry-season cultivation sown in between December & January on residual monsoon moisture, harvested in April-May [11], [20].

Each of these system carries its own set of cultivation methods that have refined over generations. Ahu is established by one of three approaches locally known as- Dhulia (broadcasting on dry fields, beginning March), Acchra (broadcasting on muddy land from late May), or Rowa/Kharma (transplanting into puddled fields) method. The Dhulia method involves leaving fields fallow after initial ploughing to loosen soil structure and stimulate microbial activity which is a practice that simultaneously promotes natural fertility recovery and improves monsoon water absorption. Soil clods formed after broadcasting are broken using a local mallet called Dalibari in a process known as Bon Ubhala or Khamla Bhanga. Weed management across these systems employs a range of indigenous implements specially the bullock-drawn wooden rake name Bidha in Ahu fields, manual weeding (Bon Nirani) in Sali fields and the Akra fashioned from a naturally bent tree branch used for Rowa/Kharma Ahu and Sali cultivation [11].

Apart from that Sali cultivation also follows a more elaborate transplanting sequence. Nurseries are established on elevated ground after the Bohag Bihu (traditional ethnic festival of Assam) festival in April. The farmers ploughed and puddled their field four to six times to achieve a well-structured, fertile seedbed, with earthen dams creating plots that retain water at a consistent level. Seedlings that are once 10-14 cm in height (approximately 30- 45 days after sowing) are uprooted the evening before transplanting and set into the puddled field the following morning by labourers in groups of two to three at regular spacing. Transplanting occurs between June and August by coinciding with peak monsoon rainfall. Weeding follows two to three months later highly depending on weed pressure. On the other hand, Bao cultivation mirrors the broadcast methods of Ahu with the process of sowing in April-May and harvesting in November-December [20].

However, in recent decades this traditional system has been substantially altered. Specially the Dhulia and Acchra methods have largely declined due to low productivity and HYV cultivation has progressively replaced traditional Ahu varieties in the same fields. Power tillers have displaced bullock drawn ploughs in Sali cultivation by compressing the fallow interval and reducing the microbial recovery time that traditional farmers had deliberately built into their seasonal calendar. By contrast of that the traditional practice of Bao cultivation has remained partly unchanged owing to the absence of viable HYV alternatives suited to deep-water conditions. Meanwhile, Boro cultivation has expanded markedly through capitalising on improved irrigation access and HYV seed availability to add a third crop cycle during the dry season improving food security and farm income while placing additional pressure on soil and water resources. HYV rice generally offers higher productivity with yields often ranging between 3.5-6.0 tonnes per hectare mainly depending on irrigation and input use whereas many traditional varieties commonly produce around 1.5-3.0 tonnes per hectare although some perform better under favourable local conditions. [21].

While this yield differential has driven HYV adoption to increase but it does not account for the lower input costs, greater climate resilience, and higher market premiums, superior taste, nutritional and medicinal value of traditional paddy varieties. So, it is clear from the ecological and cultivation evidence presented here is that paddy cultivation in Assam is not merely a production activity but an ecologically embedded system in which land typology, hydrology, seasonal timing, and indigenous knowledge are inseparable. This foundation is what gave rise to the ITK practices and germplasm diversity examined in the following sections.

ITK Across the Agricultural Cycle: Documentation and Rationale

The ITK practices of Assam paddy farmers represent one of the most comprehensive indigenous agricultural knowledge systems in the region. Which is developed over generations of careful observation, experimentation, adaptation and these practices address every major agronomic challenge across the production cycle. Here following table-1 cover in total 36 ITK practices organised into eight thematic categories and each with a brief explanation of the underlying agronomic or ecological rationale. What emerges from this record is not a set of arbitrary customs but a coherent, evidence-grounded management system in which every significant intervention has a functional purpose [7], [8], [9], [22], [23].

Table 1: Description of different well known Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) and the reasons behind the use of these ITKs in Assam.

Preparation Method	Description of ITKs	Purpose/Rationale behind their use
A. Seed-Bed Preparation	Suitable plot of size 0.5-1.0 katha (1 katha = 0.026 ha) near homestead or water source is selected.	Easy access to water and proximity to home for better management.
	The land selected is ploughed five times by wooden plough and harrowed six times. Farmers use kamra moi (convex side of harrow) for harrowing the land. After supplying required water to the soil, lota moi (concave side of harrow) is used to make it smooth	To break the soil and make it suitable for planting, Kamra moi breaks up clumps, while lota moi smoothens the soil.

	Seeds are kept in a topa or thali and steeped in ponds or khal for at least one night, then stored in a cool dark place covered with blue arum leaf or banana leaf.	Pre-soaking and covering aids in seed germination.
	Germinated seeds are broadcast by hand in the prepared land.	Hand broadcasting ensures even distribution of seeds.
	If floods occur, seedlings are removed from nursery beds and planted thickly in another suitable plot as <i>jou kathia</i> .	<i>Jou kathia</i> seedlings are unusually strong and more productive.
	<i>Jou kathia</i> seedlings are uprooted for final transplantation in prepared fields once flood subsides.	Final transplantation to main field ensures optimal growth.
	Cutting edges of border of the plots with local hoes locally known as <i>Kur</i> .	It lessens weed growth around the borders and reduces pest population at later stages by killing the pest hibernating in the border edges.
	In rice field during land preparation, bunds are prepared with weeds and stubbles collected from the fields and bunds are plastered with mud.	Weed growth of weeds are suppressed and run off of rain water as well as irrigation water is reduced.
	Ploughing with an initial irrigation in case of uplands or without irrigation in case of low land, well ahead of final puddling and keeping as such for 15 to 20 d after leveling until some excreta are seen on the soil surface.	This practice allows earthworms to grow facilitating decomposition of stubbles, thereby making soil more fertile both with decomposed materials as well as the earthworm excreta.

B. Transplanting Method	Plants reach a height of 20-30 cm after 20-25 days, then carefully uprooted from nursery bed and carried in bundles to the field for transplantation.	Ensures that seedlings are ready for transplantation when they are strong enough.
	In case of boro paddy, the top portion of boro rice seedlings are cut and buried/fed to the cattle before transplanting. This is usually practiced in case of tall seedlings of traditional boro rice varieties.	The cutting of top portion of the seedlings removes the eggs of stem borers and thereby reduces the stem borer attack during initial stage in the main field.
	Transplanting the seedlings in muddy place other than the main field for about 15-20 d and then uprooting and transplanting in the main field. This practice is known as <i>Kathiajowowa</i> in local language, meaning somewhat like hardening of seedlings.	This practice allows the seedlings to attain a height to suit the depth of water in the main field (usually practiced in a beel areas/depressions).
	Transplanting the left-over seedlings very closely or in a cluster in one of the corners of the main field.	Ensures quick and vigorous growth as seedlings do not suffer water stress due to drought.
C. Water management	Water is supplied from a nearby khal or pond using a sichani or lahati, and distributed uniformly.	Ensures the soil is adequately moist for seed germination and seedling growth.
	Small and shallow ponds are dug out in the corners of sali fields.	Helps retain excess summer water.
	Dykes are prepared around fields to retain rainwater	Adapted according to the nature of the land

	As per field elevation, generally farmers make their autumn rice fields are slightly higher than winter rice fields.	Ensures rainwater retention for a longer period.
	Irrigation with bamboo pipes is practiced for irrigating the crops from tube wells by splitting the bamboo in two equal halves vertically and removing the nodes which act as a pipe for carrying water.	Bamboo pipes so prepared reduce loss of irrigation water during transit and they are less costly as compared to purchased pipes. (e.g. Plastic pipes) and their availability is also high.
D. Seed Selection, Treatment and Germination	The seeds are traditionally stored by farmers in some bamboo baskets locally called “tum”. Baskets are hung in “jokhola”	to protect from rabbits and insects.
	After soaking the seeds overnight seeds are cured from water, colocasia (<i>Colocasia esculenta</i>) leaves are put at the bottom of a basket made of bamboo (locally called Pasi); soaked seeds are put on colocasia leaves until they reach the top of the basket and again covered with colocasia leaves. Seeds are left as such in room or shade until germination.	When seeds are covered with colocasia leaves it produces heat inside the soaked seeds enhancing germination of the seeds.
	Seeds are soaked overnight in salted water.	To remove bacteria from the seeds.
E. Fertility Management	Burning of stubbles before ploughing (usually practiced in uplands).	The ashes produced as result of burning of stubbles add to soil fertility. Besides pests and their eggs get burnt and therefore pest population in the subsequent crop becomes less.

	Use of cow dung	Farmers use cow dung as fertilizer because it is rich in essential nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, which improve soil fertility and enhance crop growth.
F. Interculture	Trampling between rows and/or hills of the rice plants	It facilitates aeration and suppression of weeds and thereby increases tillering.
	Broadcasting rice grains over a standing crop of rice and then allowing ducks to roam in the field helps in soil preparation.	As ducks consume the rice grains, they also peck at the soil, which helps to break it up and improve aeration.
G. Plant Protection	Application of bamboo T perches in rice field to control rice pest	Bamboo T perches offer birds elevated spots to rest and watch for pests in rice fields. By attracting birds that eat insects, snails, and rodents, these perches enhance natural pest control and support a balanced ecosystem. Additionally, inserting bamboo poles into the soil improves aeration, benefiting root growth in rice plants.
	Cutting of tips of rice seedling before transplantation	Cutting the tips of rice seedlings removes the areas where stem borers, like the yellow stem borer and rice leaf folder, lay their eggs. This disruption decreases the likelihood of infestation by interrupting their life cycle.

	Leaves of neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>) are spread in the field of kharif or summer rice and spraying with Neem leaves and seed extract at early tillering	To control pest and disease especially stem borer (<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>) and Leaf folder (<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>).
	Jute (<i>Corchorus capsularis</i>) ropes are dipped in kerosene and pulled across the paddy crop field.	Pulling jute ropes dipped in kerosene across paddy fields can repel pests like insects, rodents, and birds due to the strong smell. While not directly proven, this method might also help reduce rice diseases by physically disturbing fungal spores and disease vectors.
	Lightning of diyas/lamp in rice field at night	Fires attract rice pests like Gandhi bugs, disrupting their feeding behavior and acting as a repellent.
	Throwing chopped leaves of Keturi haldhi (<i>Cureuma zedoaria</i>) and peels of citrus fruit viz. Robab tenga (<i>Citrus grandis</i>) in the field during milking to Tillering stage	Chopped leaves and peels enrich soil with organic matter and nutrients, supporting beneficial microorganisms and reducing soil-borne pests and diseases.
	Jarmoni (<i>Eupatorium odoratum</i>) pat is swept over rice field.	Sweeping Jarmoni pat (<i>Eupatorium odoratum</i>) over rice fields releases natural compounds that repel pests and help control rice hispa (<i>Discladispa armigera</i>).
	Throwing cut pieces of stems of Kola kachu (<i>Colocasia esculenta</i>) during tillering stage	To control Case worm (<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i>)

	Broadcasting of goat excreta in rice field	Goat excreta act as repellent. The odor and composition of the excreta may create an unfavourable environment for pests, reducing their presence or limiting their damage to rice crops.
	Audio tapes, reels of discarded cassettes are tied around nursery plot at maturity period	The reels reflect light and produce sound which frighten away birds from the field
	Keeping scarecrow in nursery as well as main field	Frightens birds and prevents the birds from eating up the seeds
H. Post Harvest Practices	Keeping the stubbles of rice undisturbed avoiding ploughing and grazing by the cattle for 1-11/2 months.	Allows ratoon development of Boro rice, providing additional income with no extra investment.
	Storing dried leaves of Mahaneem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>) or Ghoraneem (<i>Melia azadirachta</i>) with rice grains in granaries or storage structures.	The odor and insecticidal properties of these leaves deter stored grain pests like weevils and grain moths.
	Leaves of Narasingha (<i>Murraya koenigii</i> ; curry leave tree) are placed on the heaps of rice grains in the storage.	Curry leaves have pesticidal properties that prevent storage insect pests.
	Using an earthen pitcher (Koloh) with a lid made of earth to store grains.	Shields grains from pests and outside moisture, preserving seed quality.
	Storing seeds in an oval-shaped bamboo structure called Topa, lined with paddy straw, with the mouth tightly covered with straw and sometimes plastered with fresh cow dung.	Protects seeds from moisture and pests, ensuring the seeds remain viable.

	Using a bamboo granary (Bhoral) on wooden posts or boulders, plastered inside with fresh cow dung and mud, and covered with a thatched or tin roof.	Provides good aeration and protects grains from pests and moisture due to its elevated and well-plastered structure.
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[11], [23], [7], [9], [8].

Functional Significance of ITK in Sustainable Agriculture

Reading across the eight sections from Table-1 there are several principles of functional sustainability emerge. Out of which, ecological substitution is perhaps the most consistent one as bamboo T-perches replace chemical insecticides by harnessing bird predation then comes split bamboo pipes replacing plastic irrigation infrastructure and organic amendments drawn from the farm environment like cow dung, neem extracts, Colocasia-based heat management that serve the functions of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides at negligible cost. These substitutions are not primitive improvisations but one of the sophisticated solutions that have been validated over centuries under local conditions.

Another suitable principle here is redundant resilience as multiple practices address the same challenge through different mechanisms by providing protection against the failure of any single method. For example, stem borer management involves seedling tip removal before transplanting (Section B), neem extract application at tillering (Section G), and night lamp trapping at the vulnerable grain filling stage (Section G). This layered approach is precisely what makes traditional systems more robust to environmental variability than single input modern systems.

Thirdly the knowledge system is inherently low-input and low-risk system based as the majority of materials like bamboo, cow dung, plant extracts, earthen vessels are either farm produced or locally available which generally helps by placing very little to no financial burden specially on smallholder farmers. This stands in sharp contrast to the capital requirements of modern input packages. It is also significant that post-harvest storage practices (Section H) remain in widespread use even as field-level methods are increasingly displaced by modern inputs. The topa, koloh, and bhoral storage structures continue to protect grain from pests and moisture at a very negligible cost which reflect their sustained practical competitiveness under local conditions. This persistence has direct implications for post-harvest infrastructure policy in the state by suggesting that investment in community level traditional storage systems may offer better returns for smallholders than the promotion of commercial storage alternatives.

The Wealth of Traditional Rice Germplasm: Assam's Living Genetic Library

The extraordinary diversity of paddy varieties cultivated in Assam is not coincidental as it is the direct biological product of the ITK system described in Section 3.2. Centuries of selective seed

saving, ecological observation, and adaptive cultivation have generated a germplasm base of exceptional depth. In particular out of the 67,760 rice accessions conserved in the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources (New Delhi) in total 6,630 originate from Assam which is nearly 10% of the national total from a single state [24]. Here, historical sources also confirm the deep antiquity of this diversity such as the Yogini Tantra (early 16th century) names up to twenty distinct paddy varieties, while the Katha Guru Charit and the Alamgirnama both attest to the sophistication of paddy cultivation across the region by the medieval period [25], [26], [27].

As mentioned earlier, there are four principal ecotypes that define Assam's rich paddy biodiversity. Out of them, Joha (Aromatic) varieties are mainly prized for grain fragrance and are deeply embedded in Assamese festive and culinary culture and they also command significant market premiums in domestic and export niche markets [28], [29]. Likewise, Chokuwa (semi-waxy) varieties are culturally valued for specific traditional preparations and offer distinctive nutritional profiles. Bora (waxy) paddy on the other hand serves important ritual and culinary functions and is particularly associated with traditional festivals. Bao varieties deep-water and red paddy types here mainly represent an ecological adaptation unmatched in the modern HYV repertoire by thriving in flood-prone lowlands that would be unproductive under any other cultivation system. Tables-2 present representative germplasm from the Ahu, Sali, Bao, and Boro seasonal categories in Assam.

Table 2: List of traditional rice varieties for different seasons and ecosystems found in Assam.

Sl. No.	Ahu Germplasm Name	Sl. No.	Sali Germplasm Name	Sl. No.	Bao Germplasm Name	Sl. No.	Boro Germplasm Name
1	<i>Au Biroin</i>	1	<i>Ronga Bora 2</i>	1	<i>Ahina Bao</i>	1	<i>Agoni shail</i>
2	<i>Au chaiyamora</i>	2	<i>Niranjana</i>	2	<i>Amona Bao 1</i>	2	<i>Amon</i>
3	<i>Au jaria</i>	3	<i>Kula Sali</i>	3	<i>Amona Bao 2</i>	3	<i>Asami baruah</i>
4	<i>Au kartika</i>	4	<i>Pakori Bora</i>	4	<i>Amona Bao 3</i>	4	<i>Au boruah</i>
5	<i>Au maloti</i>	5	<i>Borchakuwa 1</i>	5	<i>Badal 1</i>	5	<i>Badaal</i>
6	<i>Au mishri</i>	6	<i>Holl Sali 1</i>	6	<i>Badal 2</i>	6	<i>Badaal achra</i>
7	<i>Au murali</i>	7	<i>Jomuna</i>	7	<i>Bedel Bao</i>	7	<i>Baingtonbi chi</i>

8	<i>Au sahebeil</i>	8	<i>Kosari Sali</i>	8	<i>Balam Bao</i>	8	<i>Bairagi</i>
9	<i>Au terabail</i>	9	<i>Getu Sali</i>	9	<i>Bangla Bao</i>	9	<i>Balam</i>
10	<i>Aus</i>	10	<i>Laldubi</i>	10	<i>Baola Bao</i>	10	<i>Balam boruah</i>
11	<i>Aus biroin</i>	11	<i>Nol bora</i>	11	<i>Basudev</i>	11	<i>Banashpat i</i>
12	<i>Aus murali</i>	12	<i>Kola pakhi</i>	12	<i>Bedel Bao 1</i>	12	<i>Banaspho ol</i>
13	<i>Baag murali</i>	13	<i>Santi bora</i>	13	<i>Biroi</i>	13	<i>Baowa</i>
14	<i>Babu murali</i>	14	<i>Helosi bora</i>	14	<i>Betguti Bao</i>	14	<i>Bhoshi Bruah</i>
15	<i>Bala</i>	15	<i>Kola bordhan</i>	15	<i>Betnasali Bao</i>	15	<i>Biroin baruah</i>
16	<i>Bamurah</i>	16	<i>Mekuri sali</i>	16	<i>Betu 1</i>	16	<i>Borho baruah</i>
17	<i>Banshpati</i>	17	<i>Bor jahingia</i>	17	<i>Bezel Bao</i>	17	<i>lakhaiya</i>
18	<i>Baurosh murali</i>	18	<i>Uja Sali</i>	18	<i>Bhuspuri Bao</i>	18	<i>Latha</i>
19	<i>Bhasha murali</i>	19	<i>Pamoi Sali</i>	19	<i>Boga Amona</i>	19	<i>Madhab shail</i>
20	<i>Borho kartika</i>	20	<i>Bordubi3</i>	20	<i>Boga Balam</i>	20	<i>Mokon</i>
21	<i>Burhi murali</i>	21	<i>Ahu joha</i>	21	<i>Bogadhepa1</i>	21	<i>Mukta</i>
22	<i>Chengri</i>	22	<i>Arab joha</i>	22	<i>Bogadhepa2</i>	22	<i>Nimuri</i>
23	<i>Chengridhan</i>	23	<i>Kola joha 1</i>	23	<i>Itaguri</i>	23	<i>Nimuridha n</i>
24	<i>Chhatoki</i>	24	<i>Kola Joha2</i>	24	<i>Jaldubi1</i>	24	<i>Pani baruah</i>
25	<i>Chotto kartika</i>	25	<i>Khorika joha</i>	25	<i>Jaldubi2</i>	25	<i>Pankai</i>
26	<i>Dolu murali</i>	26	<i>Konjoha 1</i>	26	<i>Jalaprova</i>	26	<i>Poshu shail</i>
27	<i>Dumai</i>	27	<i>Konjoha2</i>	27	<i>Jeng Bao</i>	27	<i>Puti baruah</i>
28	<i>Dumaiya</i>	28	<i>Boga joha</i>	28	<i>Julee 1</i>	28	<i>Rata</i>

29	<i>Ekochali</i>	29	<i>Bogi joha</i>	29	<i>Julee 2</i>	29	<i>Sahebail baruah</i>
30	<i>Fakir kaskas</i>	30	<i>Kola kunkuni joha</i>	30	<i>Jul Bao</i>	30	<i>Shail baruah</i>
31	<i>Gul murali</i>	31	<i>Boga kunkuni joha</i>	31	<i>Kajoli Bao</i>	31	<i>Shoulorpona</i>
32	<i>Guldhan</i>	32	<i>Betguti joha</i>	32	<i>Kusumser Bao</i>	32	<i>Terabail</i>
33	<i>Harichak</i>	33	<i>Koli joha</i>	33	<i>Panjhali Bao</i>	33	<i>Tulshimala</i>
34	<i>Izong</i>	34	<i>Konbogi joha</i>	34	<i>Rajshree Bao</i>	34	<i>Tupa</i>
35	<i>Kachalu</i>	35	<i>Mukuta joha</i>	35	<i>Ujla Bao</i>	35	<i>Tupa baruah</i>
36	<i>Kaimurali</i>	36	<i>Boga manikimadhuri</i>	36	<i>Voidehi Bao</i>	36	<i>Tupa shail</i>
37	<i>Kakimakra</i>	37	<i>Bhugi joha</i>	37	<i>Sataria Bao</i>	37	<i>Tupirbhat a</i>
38	<i>Kala dumai</i>	38	<i>Chubon joha</i>	38	<i>Jimosayab Bao</i>	38	<i>Uba badaal</i>

[30], AAU-Zonal Research Station, North Lakhimpur; [31]; [28].

These varieties possess agronomic and sensory characteristics like submergence tolerance, compatibility with low-input rainfed management, distinctive aroma, texture, and nutritional profiles that modern HYVs cannot replicate. Their value therefore extends beyond cultural significance. They constitute a genetic reservoir of traits such as flood tolerance, drought resilience, disease resistance that plant breeders will increasingly require in the future as climate change makes current growing conditions more erratic. The erosion of this germplasm base specially driven by the HYV adoption trends quantified in the following Section, therefore represents not only a cultural loss but a narrowing of the options available for future food system adaptation [24], [26], [27], [29].

The Technological Transition: Change, Displacement, and Consequences

Against the backdrop of a rich and functionally coherent traditional system the pace of technological change in Assam's agriculture since the late 1980s is striking. Although the Green Revolution reached many Indian states in the 1960s, its effect in Assam was not felt until the late 1980s specially when HYV seeds and power tillers were first adopted. This transformation has been driven by mainly three interrelated forces in the state and those are- biological innovation (HYV

introduction), chemical inputs (fertilisers and pesticides), and mechanisation (tractors and power tillers) [11], [32]. Following table 4 provides a statistical profile of these changes across a 20 years period.

Table 4: Changes in agricultural technology adoption in Assam, 2010-2025

Year	Area under HYV Seeds (ha)	Irrigated Area (ha)	Fertiliser Use (tonnes)	Tractors (No.)	Power Tillers (No.)
2005	1366695	69397.28	189444	1468	1190
2010	15,12,393	1,68,853	2,40,485	1,815	1,321
2015	17,64,532	1,78,651	2,86,433	3,118	1,828
2020	18,28,375	2,58,205	2,89,383	4,781	1,830
2023	18,13,282	2,34,956	2,67,947	2,082	3,386
2025	16,68,568	2,99,508	2,83,224	604	1,816

Source: Statistical Handbook of Assam, 2005-2025 [19].

The area under HYV seeds expanded from approximately 1.37 million hectares in 2005 to 1.83 million hectares in 2020 which is a total of 34% increase over fifteen years, before a marginal decline to 1.81 million hectares in 2023 and a further retreat to 1.67 million hectares by 2025. This expansion directly corresponds to a contraction in the cultivation of traditional Ahu, Sali, and Bao paddy varieties documented in Section 4.4, which are being replaced by HYVs selected for yield rather than ecological resilience, sensory quality, or cultural compatibility. The irrigated area grew from just 69,397 hectares in 2005 to 258,205 hectares in 2020 and continued rising to 299,508 hectares by 2025 and a more than fourfold increase reflecting a deepening shift away from the rain-fed water management strategies catalogued in Table-1 and a growing structural dependence on engineered irrigation infrastructure [19], [32].

The rise in fertiliser consumption can also be seen from 189,444 tonnes in 2005 to 289,383 tonnes in 2020 representing a 53% increase in chemical inputs over fifteen years that directly substitutes for the organic fertility management system described in Section 4.2, Section E. A modest easing to 283,224 tonnes by 2025 does not reverse this trajectory. The ecological consequences are well-documented too- soil acidification, disruption of microbial communities, and nutrient imbalances that undermine the long-term productivity that the traditional system was specifically designed to maintain. Meanwhile, the number of tractors is more than tripled between 2005 and 2020 (from 1,468 to 4,781) before collapsing sharply to just 604 units by 2025, while power tillers surged to 3,386 units by 2023, indicating a substitution toward smaller machinery rather than any withdrawal from mechanisation. Mechanisation at both scales compresses the fallow interval between ploughing and

transplanting, eliminating the earthworm-mediated fertility cycle described in Table-1 and reducing the microbial recovery time that traditional farmers had built into their seasonal calendar [19], [11].

The consequences of this transition extend beyond the ecological. The community-based labour exchange systems embedded in transplanting and pest-scouting in which neighbours cooperate across fields in ways that build social capital as well as agricultural productivity are eroded when individual machines replace collective effort. Small-scale farmers without access to credit for power tillers and HYV seed packages are structurally disadvantaged which deepening rural economic inequality in the state. The transition here is, in short not merely a change in technique but a reorganisation of the socio-ecological relationships through which Assam's farming communities have historically managed their landscapes [11], [32].

Weighing the Trade-offs: Productivity Against Sustainability

The transition described in Section 4.4 is not without merit. In particular, HYV cultivation under irrigated conditions yields almost 4-6 tonnes per hectare, compared with 1.5-2.5 tonnes per hectare for traditional varieties under rainfed low-input management [21]. For farmers facing food deficits, market demands, and population pressure, this yield advantage is real and significant. The expansion of Boro cultivation during the dry season has added an additional crop cycle that enhances food security and household income. These are not trivial gains and any balanced assessment of Assam's agricultural transition must acknowledge them.

However, Table-5 presents a more comprehensive comparison of the two systems across multiple dimensions of performance and the picture that emerges is considerably more nuanced than a simple yield comparison suggests.

Table 5: Comparative performance of traditional and HYV-based agricultural systems in Assam

Dimension	Traditional System	Hyv-Based System
Yield per hectare	1.5–2.5 tonnes (rainfed)	4–6 tonnes (irrigated)
External input requirement	Low (organic, locally sourced)	High (fertilisers, pesticides, irrigation)
Climate and flood resilience	High (ecotype-specific adaptation)	Moderate to low (as modified with limited specific quality)
Agro-biodiversity	High (multiple ecotypes, local cultivars)	Low (narrow genetic base)
Soil health over time	Maintained (organic management)	Often degraded (acidification, compaction)
Cultural and food value	High (aromatic, waxy, nutritional, medicinal varieties)	Low (yield-optimised, uniform grain)

Market premium potential	High for specialty types for their specific premium quality (eg: Joha, Bora, Chakuwa)	Low to moderate (commodity market)
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Source: [24], [11], [33], [34], [8].

As Table-5 illustrates, traditional systems outperform HYV-based systems on every dimension except yield per hectare under optimal conditions. Their lower external input requirements make them more economically accessible to marginal and smallholder farmers. Their climate and flood resilience quality specially exemplified by Bao paddy varieties that survive prolonged inundation is directly relevant to a region where flooding is both historically frequent and projected to intensify under climate change. The higher agro-biodiversity of traditional systems provides ecological stability through diversified production and genetic buffering against pest and disease outbreaks. Long-term soil health under organic management is demonstrably superior to the soil condition that emerges after sustained chemical fertilisation and the market premium potential of specialty varieties such as Joha increasingly recognised in domestic and international niche markets offers smallholders a value-chain advantage that commodity HYV production cannot match [24], [33], [34].

The key insight from this comparison is that the choice between traditional and modern agricultural systems is not a binary one between low-productivity tradition and high productivity modernity. It is a multidimensional trade-off in which the most productive option depends on what is being optimised either it is short-term yield, long-term soil health, household income stability, climate resilience, or biodiversity conservation. Specially for many of Assam's smallholder farmers particularly those in flood-prone or rain-fed areas without access to reliable irrigation traditional systems may offer the more rational and risk appropriate choice. Policy frameworks that treat HYV adoption as a universal development target risk misallocating support and unknowingly destroying the ecological and cultural infrastructure on which the region's long-term food security depends [11], [24], [33], [34].

Conclusion and Recommendations:

This study has explored three interrelated dimensions of Assam's agricultural heritage- the ITK practices that sustain traditional farming, the rice germplasm diversity those practices have generated and maintained and the technological transition now threatening both. Across all three dimensions here the evidence points to the same conclusion mainly that Assam possesses an agricultural heritage of outstanding ecological, cultural, and scientific value that is under accelerating pressure from the adoption of high-input, yield-oriented modern systems.

The 36 ITK practices documented in Table-1 demonstrate that traditional Assamese farming is not a pre-scientific foundation but a sophisticated, multi-layered management system whose ecological rationality is fully consistent with contemporary principles of agroecology. The 6,630 rice accessions that Assam contributes to the national gene pool, spanning four ecotypes adapted to environments

ranging from submergence prone lowlands to fragrant paddy fields constitute a genetic resource of global significance for future food system adaptation. And the 21% expansion in HYV area and 20% rise in fertiliser use recorded between 2010 and 2020 represent a pace of displacement that if its continued then risks permanent loss of both [19], [24].

The study reaffirms that sustaining traditional paddy systems in Assam is not only a matter of cultural preservation but a strategic pathway towards achieving ecologically resilient and economically viable agriculture in the face of global environmental change. On this basis, the following recommendations are offered:

For policymakers, the priority should be to create economic environments in which traditional paddy variety cultivation is viable. This requires strengthening GI protection for high-value varieties, establishing procurement price support for traditional paddy too and integrating ITK documentation into state agricultural extension curriculum so that traditional knowledge is positioned as a complement to modern agronomy rather than an obstacle to it.

From research perspective also further research with systematic ethnobotanical surveys and participatory field trials are urgently needed. Comparative studies quantifying the productivity, soil health, resilience, and economic outcomes of traditional versus HYV management under Assam's diverse agro-climatic conditions will provide the evidence base that policy decisions currently lack. Particular attention should be given to the agro-ecological and economic performance of technology blending systems.

For farming communities and development organisations, community seed banks and Farmer Field Schools offer proven institutional frameworks for conserving germplasm, transmitting knowledge and testing integrated approaches. Supporting and scaling these institutions is perhaps the single most effective near-term action available to those committed to sustaining Assam's agricultural traditions.

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